

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for SLC25A11 (UniProt ID: Q02978) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Abstract

The mitochondrial 2-oxoglutarate/malate carrier protein, or SLC25A11, is a solute carrier protein known for transporting oxoglutarate into the mitochondria. Here we have characterized six SLC25A11 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: Q02978, *SLC25A11*, SLC25A11, solute carrier family 25 member 11, Mitochondrial 2-oxoglutarate/malate carrier protein, OGCP, alpha-oxoglutarate carrier, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

The Mitochondrial 2-oxoglutarate/malate carrier protein (SLC25A11) facilitates the transport of the metabolite 2-oxoglutarate across through the mitochondrial inner membrane (1), a process crucial for metabolic functions within the organelle (2). Beyond its role in cancer prevention (3-5), *SLC25A11* was also identified as a novel candidate gene associated with late-onset Alzheimer's disease patients (6).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (7-9). Here we evaluated the performance of six commercial antibodies for SLC25A11 for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of SLC25A11 properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (10).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (11).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from wild type (WT) and KO cell lines (12, 13). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the PaxDb "Protein Abundance Database" ([RRID:SCR_018910](https://paxdb.org/)) and identified HEK 293T as a suitable cell line that expresses the target at 545 ppm (parts per million), which is the abundance of SLC25A11 with reference to the entire expressed proteome and includes HEK 293T in the top 10% expression systems for this protein. HEK 293T was therefore modified with CRISPR/Cas9 to KO the corresponding *SLC25A11* gene (Table 1).

A *SLC25A11* KO HAP1 cell line is also commercially available at Horizon Discovery (Table 1). When we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, [RRID:SCR_017655](https://depmap.org/)) transcriptomics database, we found that HAP1 cells express the SLC25A11 transcript at 5.2 which is greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1) that we have found to be a suitable cut-off (7).

To screen all antibodies by western blot, HEK 29T WT and *SLC25A11* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with six SLC25A11 antibodies in

parallel (Figure 1A). Figure 1B shows a western blot with one selected antibody to compare the levels of SLC25A11 expression in HAP1 and HEK 293T and confirm the KO status of the commercial HAP1 cell line.

We then assessed the capability of all six antibodies to capture SLC25A11 from HEK 293T protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific SLC25A11 antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

In conclusion, we have screened six SLC25A11 commercial antibodies by western blot and immunoprecipitation by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human HEK 293T WT and *SLC25A11* KO cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in both applications (7). Several high-quality antibodies that successfully detect SLC25A11 were identified in both applications. Researchers who wish to study SLC25A11 in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available SLC25A11 antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in SLC25A11 only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. SLC25A11 experts invited to analyze and interpret observed banding patterns in western blots.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (10). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot and immunoprecipitation are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (10). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (14, 15). HEK293T *SLC25A11* KO clone was generated with low passage cells using an open-access protocol available on Zenodo: zenodo.org/record/3875777. The gRNA sequence used to introduce a STOP codon in the *SLC25A11* gene is: GCTGTGATTGGCATGACCGC.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120. Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429. Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

HEK 293T WT and *SLC25A11* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL

(Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) Or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (rabbit antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D). Tubes were rocked for ~1 h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HEK 293T WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 $\times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate overnight (~18 h) at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on a precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

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Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Montreal Neurological Institute	-	CVCL_0063	HEK 293T	WT
Montreal Neurological Institute	-	CVCL_A4PB	HEK 293T	<i>SLC25A11</i> KO
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC002127c012	CVCL_TM09	HAP1	<i>SLC25A11</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the SLC25A11 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab155196	GR138713-38	AB_2885094	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP43849	QC17332-190914	AB_2048075	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP43850	QC14277	AB_10641544	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.50	Wb
GeneTex	GTX101761	40877	AB_11174834	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	12253-1-AP	17150	AB_2877840	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.40	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	PA5-96958	Wb3187954A	AB_2808760	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.23	Wb

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Figure 1: SLC25A11 antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: SLC25A11 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: SLC25A11 antibody screening by western blot.

A) Lysates of HEK 293T WT and *SLC25A11* KO were prepared, and 25 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated SLC25A11 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab155196 at 1/1000, ARP43849 at 1/200, ARP43850 at 1/200, GTX101761 at 1/1000, 12253-1-AP at 1/1000, PA5-96958 at 1/200. Exceptions were given for antibodies ARP43849, ARP43850 and PA5-96958 which were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. **B)** Lysates of HEK 293T and HAP1 (WT and *SLC25A11* KO) were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the SLC25A11 antibody 12253-1-AP used at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 34 kDa.

Figure 2: SLC25A11 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HEK 293T lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated SLC25A11 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated SLC25A11 antibody. For western blot, 12253-1-AP was used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate.